

Survey

Acceptance of Appearance of Tooth Using Silver Diamine Fluoride By Urban & Rural Parents : A Survey

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Objective

This study aims to identify and knowledge the chances of acceptance level of parents for use of silver diamine fluoride (SDF) application in treating and arresting dental caries with the help of questionnaire made of 10 general questions given to both rural and urban parents coming to dental college in Bahadurgarh and Jhajjar region.

Method: A universal non-probability sampling technique was employed to recruit parents visiting the Outpatient Department between July 2022-Sept 2022 for the treatment of dental caries of their children. Considering the prevalence of dental caries among children aged 3-7 years. A questionnaire prepared by Alshari et al. was used as a data collection tool in this research. This questionnaire was first tested among 50 participants to confirm its adequacy. Face validity was established after reviewing the questionnaire by two subject experts. This positive feedback showed that no further changes were needed. A demographic item was included to assess the knowledge and acceptance rate of SDF in relation to the lives of parents/caregivers living in the villages of Jhajjar and urban parents of Bahadurgarh

Result: Rural males and females accepted staining on posterior teeth with 80% and 85.7% respectively and on anterior teeth 20% and 14.28% respectively. Urban males and females acceptance rate for posterior teeth was 100% and 87.5% respectively and for anterior teeth 0% and 12.5% respectively

Conclusion: This study concluded that most parents accept this treatment for their children's milk teeth, and the acceptance of posterior teeth is increasing compared to anterior teeth. Acceptance was higher among the rural population than the urban population.

Keywords: Silver Diamine Fluoride, Caries Arrest, Rural And Urban, Parent Acceptance

Introduction

Tooth decay is a global problem that is growing exponentially at an alarming rate. According to recent statistics by Kassebaum et al. 1, 60-90% of pre-school and preschool children worldwide are affected, or more than 621 million children. Management of conventional restorative caries in very young children is difficult and may require advanced medical management such as general anesthesia and sedation. Silver diamine fluoride (SDF) is an anti-caries

that is safe for pre-cooperative children, including those with special medical needs. With evidence-based safety, feasibility of use, and cost-effectiveness, SDF has the potential to revolutionize communities and pediatric dentistry.³ The disadvantage of this material is that it can stain the teeth black.

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The advantages of preventing caries with minimal distress to the child outweigh its disadvantages, particularly when access to dental care is constrained.⁴ SDF treatment offers stabilising effects on caries. Following a successful stabilisation phase and incorporating heightened preventive regimes focused on dietary control and strict oral hygiene practices can halt the progression of caries.^{2,5} Applying 38% of SDF solution twice a year has shown a caries arrest rate of 84.8%.⁶ A formulation of 38% SDF with potassium iodide (KI), which is applied as a separate reagent, is the combination that is currently in use.

Application of KI after SDF reduced the degree of dark staining caused by adverse effects of SDF application. Available evidence suggests that SDF at a concentration of 38% is recommended by the American Dental Association (ADA) and strongly recommended by the US Academy. Study of Pediatric Dentistry (AAPD) as a preventive measure focusing on a comprehensive management program for pediatric dentistry (AAPD) to reduce active cavity lesions in precocious young children and those with medical complications. It is well established in literature that parents showed statistically significant aesthetic tolerability for the application of SDF in posterior teeth as compared to the anterior dentition.^{3,8} Moreover, a study by Zhi et al. depicted that the easy and pain-free application of SDF compared to the conventional drill-and-fill approach was considered advantageous by parents.⁹ This implies that lack of knowledge could be another barrier in the acceptability of SDF.

Parental acceptance of SDF treatment was higher when they were given more information about this minimally invasive treatment and were allowed to make more informed choices. The literature supports a significant relationship between parental acceptance of SDF and children's cooperation. According to Baqer et al. 10, parents are more receptive when their children are not cooperative. In scenarios where the child was cooperative and could be treated under local anesthesia, only 27% chose SDF for the anterior teeth and 54% wanted to treat the posterior teeth. However, when children required general anesthesia for oral rehabilitation, the preference for SDF treatment increased to 69% for posterior teeth and 60% for anterior teeth. Especially as an alternative to general anesthesia, it may be accepted by caregivers because of its safety, convenience, and cost-effectiveness.^{4,12}

The aim of this study was to compare parental perception and acceptance of appearance SDF treatment on teeth. This study is novel in its attempt to understand the acceptability of this relatively recent dental material, known as SDF, as an alternative to complex and costly treatment modalities which may otherwise involve loss of tooth structure or the administration of conscious sedation or general anaesthesia.

Materials and Methods

This survey-based cross-sectional study was conducted among parents/caregivers of children with caries at the paediatric dentistry department. A universal non-probability sampling technique was employed to recruit parents visiting the Outpatient Department between July 2022–Sept 2022 for the treatment of dental caries of their children. Considering the prevalence of dental caries among children aged 3–7 years in Jhajjar and Bahadurgarh, the sample size was calculated using the OpenEpi calculator which determined the number to be 50 with a 95% level of confidence, 90% study power, and 10% attrition rate.¹³ Inclusion criteria are parents with children aged 3–7 who can read and understand English. The participants were verbally guided to complete the questionnaire and then written consent was obtained. A questionnaire prepared by Alshamari et al. It was used as a data collection tool in this research. This questionnaire was first tested among 50 participants to confirm its adequacy. Face validity was established after reviewing the questionnaire by two subject experts. This positive feedback showed that no further changes were needed. A demographic item was included to assess the knowledge and acceptance rate of SDF in relation to the lives of parents/caregivers living in the villages of Jhajjar and urban parents of Bahadurgarh.

Data analysis

The data were analysed using SPSS (version 23.0, IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA) data management software. Descriptive statistics for categorical variables were presented as frequencies. The chi-square test was used to compare the groups to find an association between dependent variables (knowledge of SDF treatment, parent acceptance of SDF treatment) and independent variables, including parents' gender, age, education, economic status, and area of residence. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Child Age	N(%)
3-5 yrs	26 (52%)
5-7 yrs	24 (48%)
Parental Gender	
Male	24 (48%)
Female	26 (52%)
Human settlement	
Rural	25 (50%)
Urban	25 (50%)

Figure1 : 50 parents participated in the research. Socio-demographic data of participating subjects is as follows:-

Figure 2: Participants were divided into 4 groups: rural males(24%), rural females(26%), urban males(24%) and urban females(26%) to know whether the parental gender and human settlement influence the acceptance of sdf.

Figure 3: Parental acceptance of SDF treatment was affected by the location of the teeth.

Chart 3: Effect of level of education on the acceptance of treatment is as follows

Discussion

The SDF panel of the American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry (AAPD) backs using 38% SDF in arresting the cavitated caries lesions of primary teeth for the extensive caries management program and after every application of 38% SDF solution only 0.2 mg fluoride is released which is far under the probably toxic dosage of 5 mg/kg and in our study 55% of respondents were unaware of exact percentage. Ezzeldin T, Al-Awasi KA, Bader RM, et al. in 2021 stated awareness of SDF was found to be 73.6% among specialists, 54.9% among graduates and 29.6% among students which was similar to our study whereas awareness of HALL technique for stainless steel crown in pediatric dentistry was found statistically similar in all participants groups i.e. 42.7% in students, 55.5% in graduates and 54.9% in specialist group ($p = 0.125$). The study concluded that non-invasive techniques are very useful tools in general but specifically during Covid-19 pandemic where they can play a major role in preventing the spread of infection, arresting decay, alleviating pain and anxiety without resorting to aggressive treatment like pulp treatment/extraction C et al in 2020 concluded graduating students appear inclined to utilize SDF upon entering private practice. Despite being preventable, untreated childhood caries is currently a leading chronic dental disease with significant impact on development, function, and quality of life in growing children.¹⁵ With nearly 530 million children affected by dental caries each year, the problem presents as a "silent epidemic".¹⁶ Therefore, an in-depth exploration to tackle the growing burden of childhood dental caries is indispensable. Lower socioeconomic strata of underdeveloped countries with high levels of unmet oral health care essentials emphasizes the need for cost effective and less invasive treatment options that cater to the needs of the masses.¹⁷ SDF application is one of the minimally invasive treatment modalities for carious teeth in children. Although international studies have been published on SDF acceptance, there is a scarcity of literature on parental acceptance of SDF treatment in this part of the world, with a vacuum for further studies. The present study investigated the parental acceptance of the utilization of SDF on their child's teeth. The parents were divided according to gender and human settlement. It was found that 83.3% rural males, 58.33% rural females, 41.6% urban males and 50% urban females accepted this treatment which shows that urban people and female participants are more inclined to esthetics.

More parents accepted staining associated with SDF on their child's primary teeth because they understood that it will exfoliate eventually. This result is similar to finding obtained by Gordon et al.

Parents judged staining on anterior teeth to be esthetically not acceptable. Rural males and females accepted staining on posterior teeth with 80% and 85.7% respectively and on anterior teeth 20% and 14.28% respectively. Urban males and females acceptance rate for posterior teeth was 100% and 87.5% respectively and for anterior teeth 0% and 12.5% respectively. It was because staining will be less visible on posterior teeth. This agrees with the finding obtained by Gordon et al and Crystal et al.

There was a little effect of level of education on the acceptance as 55.8% graduate people and 62.5% high school passed people accepted this treatment.

Conclusion

This study concluded that most parents accept this treatment for their children's milk teeth, and the acceptance of posterior teeth is increasing compared to anterior teeth. Acceptance was higher among the rural population than the urban population. Although SDF is a convenient and economical way to prevent the spread of caries, operators were skeptical about the acceptability of SDF prior to the initiation of treatment. Acceptance was higher for participants from urban areas than those from rural areas. Careful discussion of the benefits of SDF can lead to current acceptance among parents, especially if children are uncooperative with routine repairs and intend to avoid treatment under general anesthesia. Perform dental procedures on children and record their reactions. Factors affecting parents' acceptance of SDF have great potential to be evaluated and this can be considered as a future direction for research.

References

1. Sheiham A, Williams DM, Weyant RJ, et al. Billions with oral disease: a global health crisis—a call to action. *J Am Dent Assoc* 2015;146(12):861–4.
2. Petersen PE, Lennon MA. Effective use of fluorides for the prevention of dental caries in the 21st century: the WHO approach. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol* 2004;32(5):319–21.
3. Petersen PE, Ogawa H. Prevention of dental caries through the use of fluoride— the WHO approach. *Community Dent Health* 2016;33(2):66–8.
4. Thompson FE, McNeel TS, Dowling EC, et al. Interrelationships of added sugars intake, socioeconomic status, and race/ethnicity in adults in the United States: National Health Interview Survey, 2005. *J Am Diet Assoc* 2009;109(8):1376–83.

5. Bagramian RA, Garcia-Godoy F, Volpe AR. The global increase in dental caries. A pending public health crisis. *Am J Dent* 2009;22(1):3–8.
6. Chaffee BW, Rodrigues PH, Kramer PF, et al. Oral health-related quality-of-life scores differ by socioeconomic status and caries experience. *Community Dent Oral Epidemiol* 2017;45(3):216–24.
7. Crystal YO, Niederman R. Silver diamine fluoride treatment considerations in children's caries management. *Pediatr Dent* 2016;38(7):466–71.
8. Horst JA. Silver fluoride as a treatment for dental caries. *Adv Dent Res* 2018; 29(1):135–40.
9. Gregory D, Hyde S. Root caries in older adults. *J Calif Dent Assoc* 2015;43(8): 439–45.
10. Featherstone JDB. Remineralization, the natural caries repair process—the need for new approaches. *Adv Dent Res* 2009;21:4–7.
11. Niederman R, Feres M, Ogunbodede E. Dentistry. In: Debas HT, Donkor P, Gawande A, et al., editors. *Essential surgery: disease control priorities* Washington, DC: The 2015 International Bank for Reconstruction and Development/The World Bank; 2015. p. 173–95.
12. Mei ML, Li QL, Chu CH, et al. Antibacterial effects of silver diamine fluoride on multi-species cariogenic biofilm on caries. *Ann Clin Microbiol Antimicrob* 2013; 12:4.
13. Mei ML, Ito L, Cao Y, et al. Inhibitory effect of silver diamine fluoride on dentine demineralisation and collagen degradation. *J Dent* 2013;41(9):809–17.
14. Chu CH, Lo EC. Microhardness of dentine in primary teeth after topical fluoride applications. *J Dent* 2008;36(6):387–91.
15. Mei ML, Nudelman F, Marzec B, et al. Formation of fluorohydroxyapatite with silver diamine fluoride. *J Dent Res* 2017;96(10):1122–8.
16. Mei ML, Chu CH, Low KH, et al. Caries arresting effect of silver diamine fluoride on dentine carious lesion with *S. mutans* and *L. acidophilus* dual-species cariogenic biofilm. *Med Oral Patol Oral Cir Bucal* 2013;18(6):e824–31.
17. Duangthip D, Fung MHT, Wong MCM, et al. Adverse effects of silver diamine fluoride treatment among preschool children. *J Dent Res* 2018;97(4):395–401.